

LEASING WITH THE APPLICATION OF THE MECHANISM OF PUBLIC-PRIVATE PARTNERSHIP IN THE HOUSING AND COMMUNAL SERVICES OF UKRAINE**Konyev A.**

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ABSTRACT

Housing and communal services (HCS) is a significant socio-economic sector. The conditions and quality of life of the population depend on the level of development of this sphere. The article deals with the investment methods of financing innovative activities in the sphere of housing and communal services. According to the authors, one of the priority tools for reforming this sector is the development of leasing operations within the mechanism of public-private partnership. The study of terminology of leading experts in this area allowed the authors to define the leasing operations of innovative activities of the housing and utilities sector using the mechanism of public-private partnership.

The authors of the article developed the organizational and economic process of leasing transactions with the direct participation of the state for the development of innovative activities in the sphere of housing and communal services. The scheme is presented, which allows you to trace the relationship of the subjects of the leasing transaction with the participation of the state step by step. The main advantages for each of the subjects of the transaction deserve special attention. The directions of state stimulation, necessary for effective functioning of the mechanism of leasing operations in the sphere of housing and communal services, are offered.

Thus, the study shows the need for the development of leasing transactions with the direct participation of the mechanism of public-private partnership, which will have a positive impact on investment and innovation activities of housing and communal services. Implementation of the proposed innovative and investment solutions based on leasing will increase the efficiency of housing and communal enterprises, and therefore, the overall management efficiency of housing and communal sphere in Ukraine as a whole, which, in turn, will have a favorable effect on the production of equipment of related industries.

Keywords: housing and communal services, state regulation, industry reform, public-private partnership; leasing operations; innovative activities; subjects of the leasing transaction.

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JEL Classification: A10, L30, L31, L97, C10

Introduction: Housing and communal services (HCS) is a sphere that combines a multi-branch complex, covering more than 30 types of activities, providing continuous production of housing and communal services, as well as forming qualitative indicators of the environment of human life support. Currently, there are problems in the housing and utilities sector (high level of depreciation of the housing stock and utility networks, low quality of services to the population, inefficient management system of housing and utilities enterprises, etc.), which require urgent solutions, because the state and level of development of housing and communal services is a deterrent to socio-economic development of the country [1, p. 353-360].

To solve the problems in this sector there is a need to search and implement effective management mechanisms, i.e. it is necessary to understand, through which modern tools of financing will be implemented innovative development of the sphere of housing and communal services. The introduction of new innovative ap-

proaches and methods of attracting investment resources in Ukraine will give the country's economy the opportunity to overcome obstacles in financing subsidized and unprofitable areas such as housing and communal services and form the basis for further positive development and optimal regulation of the economy.

These measures will raise the living standards of the population and renovate fixed assets by introducing advanced technologies. According to the authors of the article, one of the most rational and effective tools for financing innovative activities of housing and communal services is a leasing mechanism with the direct participation of the state. The concept of using the mechanism of public-private partnership to solve the problems of socio-economic development of the country is now widely used [2, p. 18].

Practice shows that innovative enterprises (including housing and communal orientation) are very effective, quantity of innovations per unit of expenses, as a rule, in them more than in other comparable enterprises. Financial opportunities of leasing as a highly effective

and extremely flexible investment tool are wide, which allows you to quickly use in the production of scientific and technological progress, as well as on specific examples to understand the economic mechanisms of the leasing business in terms of the regulatory framework in the country.

Development of theoretical and methodological base, as well as mechanisms for solving the above tasks is clearly insufficient, which limits the possibility of using investment methods and improving the quality and efficiency of this sphere of activity. It is impossible to solve the problems of the housing and utilities sector without introducing new methods, mechanisms, and approaches to the financing of capital investments. Leasing should become the prevailing method and method, of course, considering industry characteristics and the influence of specific factors.

The aim of the study is to substantiate the methods of development of leasing operations using the mechanism of public-private partnership in the sphere of housing and communal services.

The methodological basis of the article is based on the system and resource-potential approaches to the object and subject under study.

Theoretical and methodological basis of the study were the scientific works of domestic and foreign scientists devoted to the theory, methodology and practice of management of housing and communal services organizations. When solving the problems of the study were used dialectical methods (analysis and synthesis, detailing and generalization, analogy, and modeling), as well as economic and statistical methods, methods of expert evaluations, observation, questioning. The implementation of the proposed investment solutions will help to increase the efficiency of housing and communal enterprises. The results of the study can be useful to specialists in the field of management, investment, and finance, dealing with the problems of reforming the system of housing and communal services and attracting investment in this sector. The main provisions and materials of the article can also be used in the educational process in the study of investment, leasing, enterprise economics.

Analysis of the research and setting of the task: Significance of development of innovative activity, leasing, in attracting financial resources by Ukrainian enterprises and organizations revealed in several works of domestic and foreign scientists and practitioners, such as: Seregin V.P., Makeeva V.G., Leshchenko M.I., Khalevinsky E.D., Gazman V.D., Inshakov O.V., Lvov D.S., Oleynik A.P., Asaul A.N, N., Osipov A.S., Serov V.M., Kazansky J.N., Coase R., North D., Clark P., Demsets G., Alchian A. and many others. The specifics of management based on the application of the mechanism of public-private partnership in the sphere of housing and communal services are reflected in the scientific works of V.V. Akimkin, Genzler, Yeshchenko, M., Fasolko, T., Mukhalchenko, H., Udovychenko, I., Grossmann M.

Despite the large number of scientific papers in the economic literature not enough elaborated questions to solve the problem of implementation, use and development of investment, specifically leasing in practical

economic sectors of the country. And the sphere of housing and communal services is not an exception. However, even though a significant number of scientific papers are devoted to the theoretical foundations, their study revealed insufficient substantiation of models and methods of management in the field of housing and communal services based on the application of the mechanism of public-private partnership in Ukraine. Solving the above problems is of scientific interest, needs further theoretical and methodological justification, as well as practical implementation with respect to the current stage of development of organizational and economic relations in the sphere of housing and communal services based on application of the mechanism of public-private partnership in Ukraine, which makes the research of the authors of the article different from the research conducted earlier in this subject area.

Results of the study: Insufficient development of management mechanisms, investment attraction, lack of financial resources in the renewal of fixed assets determine the significance and relevance of the topic of the study. The central problem of the work is leasing, but leasing is not in itself, not as an isolated phenomenon, but as an innovative investment resource in the system of renewal of fixed assets of the housing and communal sector. The analysis proved the crisis state of the communal system due to the lack of economic incentives and simple, accessible options for solving the problem of reducing the cost of heat production. High degree of depreciation of fixed assets, low level of operation, inefficient work of enterprises of communal sphere - all these factors cause imbalance of economy of the branch. Changing the situation in the direction of increasing economic and energy efficiency requires significant capital investments, and investment should be planned and systematic.

The current financial state of enterprises of communal heat and power completely excludes a systematic approach to solving the problem of providing quality heat supply to consumers at the expense of their own funds and local budgets. Consequently, the formation and implementation of the program with state support, reforming of communal heat power industry is the main basis within which it is possible to systematically implement measures for technical re-equipment of the industry with the achievement of maximum economic efficiency and real improvement of the quality of heat supply of the population and social sphere objects. Surveys of housing and communal services have shown that the main reasons for the decline in efficiency are dilapidated ways of delivering heat to consumers and their irrational use, the lack of water treatment systems, a large proportion of manual labor, the lack of modern energy-saving technologies and technological control devices, low level of service [3, p. 200].

Reform program of housing and communal services should be aimed at reconstruction and technical re-equipment of fully exhausted, economically inefficient heat supply systems of cities and settlements. The main purpose of the implementation of these measures is to transfer the communal heat industry from the technically backward and economically unprofitable "residual" sphere of the national economy to a modern high-

tech industry with a balanced economy. Measures to stabilize the situation in the sphere of housing and utility services cannot be implemented without attracting innovative forms of investment, in particular leasing. The lack of funds necessary for the introduction of highly efficient boiler, boiler and auxiliary equipment and specialized equipment, which is noted in the budgets of municipalities, makes it relevant to introduce a system of leasing using various methods of attracting financial flows.

The introduction of the leasing system will allow: introduce in the necessary quantity the means of control of qualitative and quantitative technological parameters directly affecting the consumption of fuel resources; introduce modern information technologies necessary for prompt processing of received information and making adequate managerial decisions based on the operational analysis of technological processes; provide utilities companies with modern specialized equipment; introduce modern highly efficient technologies and equipment adapted to use the cheapest for each territory fuel and energy resources in the housing and communal sector.

Compared to other ways of acquiring equipment (payment upon delivery, purchase with deferred payment, bank loans, etc.) leasing has several significant advantages:

1. Leasing makes it possible for the lessee company to expand production and establish equipment servicing without large one-time expenses and necessity of attraction of borrowed funds.

2. The problem of limited liquidity is mitigated since equipment purchase costs are evenly distributed throughout the term of the contract. At the same time funds are released for investment in other types of assets.

3. Due to that no borrowed capital is attracted, financial management of the enterprise can maintain an optimum ratio of equity and borrowed capital.

4. As lease payments are made after installation, adjustment and start-up of the equipment, the leasing recipient enterprise has an opportunity to make payments from the means coming from sale of products produced on the leased equipment.

5. Since leasing payments are made on a fixed schedule, lessee-enterprise has greater opportunities to coordinate expenses on financing capital investments.

6. Acquisition of equipment by leasing allows profitable enterprises to significantly reduce the tax base by optimizing tax deductions.

To guarantee the repayment of the loan and timely repayment of interest on the loan, it is necessary on the part of the state authorities to create a fund for financing leasing programs for the sphere of housing and communal services. Which would fully or partially participate in the projects and guarantee the leasing companies the timely repayment of the loan. We are talking about leasing, as a loan on a repayable and paid basis, the public authorities would thus be able to increase their reserves, to renew the technology park system of housing and communal services, to revive both the sphere of

production equipment necessary for communal - economy, and research in the development of new technologies, relieve social tensions, etc.

The system of reforming the sector should attract specialists and leasing companies, which have been working in this segment of the market for a long time and have an impeccable reputation. Examples of successful implementation of leasing in housing and communal services in different regions of Ukraine, and analysis of the actual specific difficulties in their implementation allow us to draw a conclusion about the feasibility of innovative methods of investment based on leasing operations.

In the domestic literature there are many definitions of the term public-private partnership, in the opinion of the authors, the most precise and complete was proposed by V. Varnavsky: "Public-private partnership is a legally formalized (usually for a fixed term), involving joint investment and risk sharing, the system of relations between the state and municipalities, on the one hand, and citizens and legal entities, on the other, the subject of which are state and/or municipal objects. [4, p. 41-50]. Public-private partnership in the housing and utilities sector should act as a special socially oriented tool of market economy, contributing to the effective development of innovative activities of the housing and utilities sector. The conceptual basis of the concept lies in the interaction of different levels of management in the sphere of housing and communal services, the delimitation of their power, authority and responsibility, the development of innovative and investment processes for innovation-oriented enterprises of housing and communal services, aimed at achieving synergy in coordinating interests, coordinating efforts and consolidating resources of its parties when implementing socially significant projects in the housing and communal services. The study of foreign experience of implementing innovations in the process of providing services to the population in the field of housing and communal services allows us to determine that an important factor influencing the effectiveness of activities is the willingness of private business to cooperate with state-owned enterprises [5, p. 963-965].

Leasing is a contractual form of public-private partnership and is a type of investment activity that combines elements of rent and credit, involving the transfer of ownership of the object of leasing to the lessee after all payments. The concept of "leasing" is widely interpreted in foreign and domestic literature. To identify the essence of leasing relations, researchers consider their legal, financial, or economic content. Leasing should be defined as a system of property relations, in which the transformation of property rights between the subjects [6, p. 464]. Currently, leasing operations in the sphere of housing and communal services are possible in the following areas: leasing of special equipment and mechanisms; leasing of high-performance equipment; leasing of automated control systems.

In the authors' opinion, the use of leasing operations in innovative activities of housing and communal services using public-private partnership mechanism is a socio-economic development institution of modern

economy in the format of institutionally organized constructive alliance, arising in connection with the implementation of the leasing agreement for the development of innovative activities of the most important sector of the country (housing and communal services). Let us consider the scheme of leasing operations for the development of innovative activities of housing and utilities sector using the mechanism of public-private partnership. The direct participants (subjects) of this mechanism are the lessee, the lessor, and the seller (property supplier). Lessee within the mechanism of public-private partnership is the organization in the sphere of housing and communal services or the state which in

accordance with the leasing agreement takes the property into lease for a certain period to develop innovative activities of housing and communal services [7, p. 465].

The seller can be an organization that sells the property required for the development of innovative activities of housing and communal services based on a purchase and sale agreement with the lessor within a specified period. Figure 1. presents organizational-economic relations of subjects of leasing transaction with the use of public-private partnership mechanism for the development of innovative activities of housing and communal services.

Figure 1. Organizational and economic process of the leasing transaction with the use of the mechanism of public-private partnership for the development of innovative activities in the sphere of housing and communal services:

- 1 - definition of the leasing subject; 2 - application of housing and communal services organizations to state authorities (approval of innovative business plan); 3 - leasing agreement conclusion; 4 - state guarantees; 5 - loan agreement; 6 - insurance agreement; 7 - purchase and sale agreement conclusion; 8 - advance payment; 9 - supply agreement; 10 - property delivery; 11 - leasing

*) Source: personal contribution of the authors

The proposed scheme allows the participants of the mechanism to consistently carry out the relationship at each stage of the organizational and economic process when investing in innovative activities of the sphere of housing and communal services. The stages of this process include the following:

1. Determining the subject of leasing (choice of property), which is an essential condition for concluding a leasing transaction. The subject of leasing for enterprises, engaged in innovation activity, can be buildings, constructions, vehicles, equipment, including enterprises and other property complexes, as well as other movable and immovable property for modernization,

technical service, provision of services to population, etc.

2. State consideration of application for implementation of innovative project of housing and communal services. Organization of housing and communal sphere applies to state executive body with request to satisfy application for development of innovative activity and submits innovative business plan of the project and in addition package of documents (feasibility report, notarized copies of constituent documents, balance sheets, bank statements on account of enterprise, tax reports and other documents). The state authority analyzes the information provided by the enterprise of

housing and communal services: on qualitative, political, and socio-economic criteria, provision of legal opportunities for project implementation. After that it forms conclusion about possibility of realization of the innovative project of housing and communal services.

3. Conclusion of leasing agreement. HCS organizations or state bodies apply to the leasing company with a commercial proposal on leasing operations, and provide a package of necessary documents, confirming the financial condition and development prospects of the HCS organization. The staff of the leasing company evaluates the objectivity of the provided information, performs a comprehensive examination of the leasing innovative project in the sphere of housing and communal services, and evaluates the lessee's solvency, level of staff qualifications, assessment of non-payment risk, etc. State authorities, in turn, provide guarantees to the leasing company. In case of a positive decision, the leasing deal is legally formalized by the lease agreement and a schedule of monthly leasing payments is drawn up.

The methodology of their calculation is formed according to the "Guidelines for calculating leasing payments". If the organization fails to make payments according to the schedule of leasing payments, the lessor has the right to confiscate the property which belongs to it by right of ownership and sell it in the secondary market. If the client makes the leasing payments according to the schedule and fully pays the amount of the contract, the ownership of the property at the end of the leasing transaction is transferred to the client at residual value. All income and profit made by the client while using the equipment is the property of the client. The organization of housing and communal services undertakes to make systematic monthly payments during the whole term of the leasing contract.

4. Then the leasing company for financing the transaction directs its own resources, if necessary, applies to a credit organization for additional attraction of funds.

5. The next step is to sign contracts of sale and delivery of the property which is the subject of leasing for the implementation of innovative activities of housing and communal services. The leasing company acquires

the property from the seller and signs the sale and purchase agreement. After the agreement is executed, the seller is obliged to transfer the property to the lessor or to the organization of housing and communal services by the act of acceptance. The leasing company together with the housing organization oversees the delivery of the equipment and other related issues. Such a scheme allows for an effective and efficient resolution of all issues that arise during this stage. Contracts are implemented starting with an advance payment and depending on agreement with the State the advance payment may be made by State authorities or the housing and communal services organization. The housing and utilities organization at its own expense maintains the property and ensures its safety, while carrying out current and capital repairs. The leased asset, transferred into temporary possession (use) of the organization of housing and communal services to carry out innovative activities, is the property of the lessor. Lessee has the right to own and use the leased asset in full.

6. The final stage assumes completion of the operation after expiration of the leasing agreement and repurchase of the leased asset by the lessee if it is stipulated in the leasing agreement. It should be noted that within the mechanism of public-private partnership the lessee can be not only housing and utility companies, but also the state. Each of the participants in the partnership pursues its own goals. The state can act as a bearer of socially significant interests and perform goal setting and controlling functions, and as a participant of economic turnover and be interested in the effectiveness of the overall results of the project and in ensuring its own commercial effect. Private partner pursues the goal of maximizing profits, i.e., commercial interest. In this regard, in the segment of commercial interest between partners it is quite appropriate to bargain about the possible division of arising profits and risks, about the nature of delegated powers and the conditions of their transfer and use [8, p. 220].

In the article the authors consider the advantages for the subjects of the transaction in the implementation of leasing transactions using the mechanism of public-private partnership for the development of innovative activities of housing and utilities organizations (Table 1).

Table 1

Advantages for the subjects of leasing transactions with the use of public-private partnership mechanism of organizations in the field of housing and communal services^{*)}

Subjects	Benefits
State	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • fulfillment of social obligations (contributes to the provision of quality services, improving the quality of life of the population); • reduction of budget expenditures; • improving the efficiency of the use of budgetary funds; • targeted nature of financial support.
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • regulation and control of the development of housing and communal services in accordance with the needs of the population, as well as the process of providing innovative housing and communal services to consumers in the subordinate territory; • an extra-budgetary source of funding for investment and innovative needs of the industry; • reduce accidents, improve the reliability of utility systems through timely replacement of infrastructure facilities, modernization, reconstruction, etc; • increasing the investment attractiveness of the industry, as well as the local and regional economy.
Organizations of the housing and utilities sector engaged in innovative activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • introduction of innovative technologies, which contributes to improving the quality of services provided to the population; • payment of leasing payments and receipt of income from the operation of the leased object; • expansion of production without large one-time investments in innovative activities of housing and communal services; • full depreciation of property and property tax savings, as it is on the balance sheet of the lessor; • reduction of taxable base by means of optimization of tax deductions; • at the end of the contract the lessee can extend the lease at a preferential rate or purchase the property at residual value; • the first payment under the leasing contract, as a rule, is made by the state.
Leasing companies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • receipt of interest in the form of monthly deductions for the use of property and attraction of new clients for conclusion of leasing contracts; • economic benefits at the expense of tax and amortization benefits established by the state; • the risk of non-return is reduced: the property leased out remains in the ownership of the lessor, the state provides guarantees, the property is subject to compulsory insurance, etc.
Seller	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • increase in sales; • receiving cash in full in a lump sum; • expansion of the customer base; • obtaining additional income due to the provision of services when selling their equipment
Credit institutions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • expansion of the loan portfolio by attracting new borrowers; • exemption from payment of profit tax, received from granting credits to the subjects of leasing, for the term of not less than three years for realization of the leasing agreement; • minimization of risks as the object of leasing acts as collateral
Insurance company	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • receipt of insurance premiums; • expansion of the client base

^{*)} Source: personal contribution of the authors

Thus, the positive side of this mechanism is that each of the subjects receives direct benefits. Despite the advantages, for the effective functioning of the mechanism of leasing operations in the sphere of housing and communal services it is necessary to implement the following directions of state stimulation:

1. Creation of the state investment leasing fund for the development of housing and communal services.
2. Development at the state and regional levels of programs for the development of leasing operations in

innovative activities in the sphere of housing and communal services.

3. Provision of additional tax benefits.
4. Formation of the normative-legal base, providing protection of legal and property interests of the subjects of leasing transactions.
5. Development of recommendations on the partnership of the state and organizations of the housing and communal services in financing innovative projects on the model of the state financial leasing.

6. Creation of an algorithm for assessing the possibility of providing leasing in the framework of public-private partnership for organizations of housing and communal services, etc.

Under the conditions of limited financial resources of both business and government, it is required to use effective financial mechanisms for the implementation of state industrial policy. One such mechanism is leasing, which has proven itself in the implementation of state transport and agricultural policies. Meanwhile, leasing is not sufficiently used by the state as a tool for the development of industry and the economy, as evidenced by comparisons between different countries. Accordingly, the most important problem of the Ukrainian economy associated with reforming the sphere of housing and communal services cannot be solved without the use of innovative and creative approaches to attract investment in fixed assets of this industry. Leasing may become a relatively new mechanism, considering the specifics and industry characteristics (low profitability, long payback period of fixed assets, acute shortage of qualified personnel, etc.) [9, p. 87-105].

The analysis of the housing and utilities sector has shown its crisis state. A separate problem is the backwardness of equipment and technology used in the housing and utilities sector. The problems of a high degree of depreciation of equipment and backwardness of equipment and technology are often combined into one problem - the need for technological modernization of the industry, which is explained by the fact that the solution of these problems is carried out simultaneously. Inefficient work of the organizations of housing and communal services causes imbalance of the whole economy of Ukraine. Changes that have taken place in the last years in the organizational structure of the housing and communal sphere enterprises (for example, management companies) are aimed at stimulating the subjects of this sphere, giving them the power and "freedom" to choose the means to achieve quality, but, unfortunately, the actual productivity and growth of the quality of services provided was lower than the predicted values.

The most important problem of the sphere of housing and communal services is the reduction of costs for production of heat and water supply. Introduction of energy-saving and cost-effective technologies requires large capital investments from organizations, which should be systematic and planned. Unfortunately, the current financial situation in the housing and utilities sector is practically ruling out a systematic approach to solving problems. Without state support, it is impossible to effectively implement the project of reforming the sector and carry out activities on technical reequipment to achieve maximum efficiency and real improvement of the quality of services in the housing and utilities sector for the population and objects of the social sphere.

Analysis of the enterprises of the sphere of housing and communal services showed that the reasons for the reduction of economic efficiency in technical terms are obsolete technologies of energy generation and net-

works of its delivery to consumers, poor water treatment system, low implementation of modern control devices, high proportion of manual labor, unscheduled and untimely maintenance of equipment, low qualification of personnel, "onstage" of work.

An important problem in the development of the industry and specifically the housing and utilities sector is the lack of qualified personnel. There are two aspects to it. The first is the shortage of qualified workers. So, out of 100% of the working staff, only 5-10% are highly qualified. One of the reasons for this situation is the loss of the training base. The second aspect of this problem is the shortage of scientific personnel related to industrial development, including the significant outflow of "brains" abroad [10, p. 242].

This problem is caused not only by low wages, but also by the inability to realize their creative potential at home. Often, heating networks of municipalities are unregulated due to irregular and infrequent adjustments. This is reflected in the overestimation, compared to the planned and estimated consumption, of the network water, return water temperatures in boilers, hot water losses on the routes, and excess or shortage of pressure at consumers. Also, there is practically no system of backup power sources, which in the absence of them in an emergency (especially in severe frost) increases the likelihood of a technological disaster and defrosting of the heat supply system.

As a result of reform measures, the housing and utilities sector should acquire qualitatively new properties, such as: reliability and continuity of the system of providing services to the population and other consumers on conditions of self-sufficiency and profitability; reducing to a minimum the occurrence of man-made negative situations; ability to self-development; ability to introduce modern energy and resource saving technologies; to level risks (economic, technological, social, human resources, etc.); to become attractive to investors the sector.

Solving the above-mentioned problems requires a set of economic measures such as: attraction of large-scale investments into the modernization and reconstruction of the main assets of the housing and communal sector; unified technical, pricing, personnel, and investment policy; and strict control over the cost of the services provided. These activities cannot be carried out without a clearly defined strategy for attracting investment, the prevailing method, in the opinion of the authors of the article, which should be leasing, considering industry characteristics and state guarantees.

The analysis of fixed assets in the housing and utilities sector has shown great potential for monetization of significant non-core assets that are not used as intended, and often just "idle". Their implementation will not only release enterprises from encumbrances (saving resources for their maintenance) but will also bring organizations of housing and communal services the funds for the initial installment on leasing equipment when updating obsolete and working at full capacity equipment.

Leasing in the sector of housing and communal services should be focused on the following directions: leasing of control systems, especially automated ones;

leasing of modern highly efficient and energy-saving equipment; leasing of units, aggregates, mechanisms, and machinery. Balanced introduction of innovations through the implementation of leasing will allow: to implement a system of quality control and optimal fuel resources consumption; to renew obsolete specialized equipment; to obtain complete, objective, and reliable information for making timely management decisions [11. p. 146].

The choice of areas for the use of leasing for the implementation of industrial policy of the state in the sphere of housing and communal services depends on the strategy of industrial policy, varieties of which are determined by the types of industrial policy, distinguished by the degree of innovation (raw materials, avant-garde technologies and comprehensive, combining the first three varieties).

The current situation in the Ukrainian economy requires the implementation of a comprehensive strategy of industrial policy. When implementing the strategy of avant-garde technologies intra-industrial leasing is used, and to stimulate the demand for innovative products that can act as the subject of leasing - industrial-economic and industrial-export versions of this instrument of industrial policy. In view of the complexity of the strategy of Ukrainian industrial policy, for its implementation it is necessary to use all areas of leasing, but with an emphasis on intra-industrial.

When using leasing as an instrument of industrial policy in the housing and utilities sector the processes of monitoring and decision-making in public leasing management change significantly: factors and problem situations in leasing management now become also factors and problem situations of industry functioning in part related to leasing activities, in developing solutions for leasing management it is necessary to study the impact of factors (problem situations) and measures being developed not only on the industrial leasing of housing and utilities companies itself [12. p. 145-158].

Conclusions: Creation of specialized information system on industrial leasing should transfer to a new level the traditional work of collecting and processing information on industrial leasing, the problem of which is that the information needed to manage leasing as an instrument of industrial policy is not formed in the country. Its tasks also include making rating of leasing companies for their inclusion in the infrastructure of industrial support.

The implementation of the proposed innovative investment solutions based on leasing will increase the efficiency of housing and communal enterprises and, consequently, the overall efficiency of management of housing and communal sphere in Ukraine as a whole, which, in turn, will have a favorable effect on the production of related industries equipment.

The measures proposed by the authors will effectively implement innovative activities of housing and

communal enterprises, which will contribute to the development of technology industry to produce housing and communal services, modernization of networks and equipment, creating new jobs, improving the quality of life, etc.

Summarizing the above, we can conclude on the expediency of leasing operations with the use of public-private partnership mechanism for the development of innovative activities of housing and communal services, as the use of this mechanism is a promising direction for the successful reform of the industry.

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